

FAMILY FOMENTATION IN RELATION TO RESULT-BASED PERFORMANCE QUALITY OF TECHNICAL, VOCATIONAL AND LIVELIHOOD STUDENTS

JESSA LOU BERNAL

Abstract. This study aimed to determine the relationship between the family fomentation and result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students during the school year 2022-2023. This study utilized the descriptive-correlational design with one hundred fifty respondents selected using simple random sampling technique. In gathering data, the researcher adapted survey questionnaires both for the family fomentation and result-based performance quality. Ethical considerations were observed in data collection. The collated data were subjected to statistical tests such as mean, Pearson's r and multiple linear regression. Findings showed that the extent of family fomentation of students is extensive, which means that the family fomentation of TVL students is oftentimes observed. The extent of result-based performance quality of students is extensive, which means that the result-based performance quality of TVL students is oftentimes observed. There was a high significant relationship between the family fomentation and result-based performance quality of students. The domains of family fomentation that influenced the result-based performance quality were emotional warmth, self-awareness and parental management. With this, the Department of Education should set aside sufficient funds for the instructional and learning materials for senior high school TVL students. This allows for the acquisition of genuine laboratory materials with high quality standard.

KEY WORDS

1. Result-based performance
2. family fomentation
3. emotional warmth
4. parental management

1. Introduction

Due to the constant changes in working life, academic institutions have had to evolve current methods to ensure their students' capability. With this, less conventional components such as project and portfolio effort have gradually been introduced into formal learning. Furthermore, expanding practical training intervals has been deemed prudent, as these will guide more relevant, systematic, and negotiable learning, providing students with a more integrated experience, particularly those in the technical, vocational and livelihood track. However, the pandemic has made the task of improving students' performance in this field much more difficult to address, as interactive and participatory activities were difficult to achieve, especially in

senior high school tracks that promote hands-on and engaging experiences for students. As a result, in the post-pandemic time, there is a massive battle against students' results quality, particularly the Technical, Vocational and Livelihood track. Teachers in Turkey as reported by Tanik-Onal and Onal (2020) encountered difficulties during the post-pandemic in handling students' feedback on any of their behaviors, inadequacy of lesson duration, limitation of learning through engaging and hands-on activities, and the lack of active participation in the lessons which are inherent in vocational concepts. In addition, the finding of Erduran (2020) stated that even though the blended instruction in secondary level has a positive impact on students' time management and timeliness of output submission in India, practicum teachers did not see the eagerness and excitement of the vocational students in performing practical and laboratory works unlike during before the pandemic. Added to this is the observed poor quality of performance as evident in their substandard outcome (Caruana et. al., 2020). Low performance and output quality among the senior high school Technical, Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) students is one of the problems that baffles many teachers in the Philippines. They were having a hard time to cope and exact solution with that particular problem (Quinones, 2020). Studying quality of performance and skills acquisition may aid students an understanding on how important to know the correlation between the two given variables. However, Sanders and Rivers (2019) found that TVL students during the return of face-to-face instruction are having difficulties in expressing and generating ideas, varied personalities which evident in their behav-

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study, which are the critical variables of the research. The independent variable of this study is the learner's family fomentation which

ior, passive and uncooperative in performing practical and laboratory works and, lack of communication between members. The problem of seeking to improve the skills of TVL students all over the Davao region still stands. As long as this problem continues to exist regardless of the situation, it is very existence continues to hinder and undermine the potential of many students in achieving a better performance in the different disciplines in TVL track (Tria, 2020). When left ignored by effective solutions that coincide with the context of today's time, Calpo (2020) argued that this could lead to long term problems such as incompetent employees' standings, scarcity of skilled professional in the field, lack of students who wish to apply for a job after they graduating from senior high school. Thus, something must be done to address the different gaps brought by the pandemic. With all of these in mind, the researcher has chosen to pursue this study. TVL students are contented to whatever performance they could show and outputs they can submit to the teachers regardless of the quality. Though teachers presented the rubrics of each performance task, still could not meet the standard. It is believed that in order to address the problem of the low-performance standings and poor results quality of TVL students, the solution should start at the grassroots level wherein the context of the teachers is put into emphasis. When researchers are given the opportunity to investigate the status of family fomentation indicators of the TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City, as well as their results quality based from their performance and output, vital information can be gathered in order to form a long-term solution to the problem.

will be measured in terms of emotional warmth, self-awareness, moral formation, and parental management; while the dependent variable is the result-based performance quality which will

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

be measured in terms of responsiveness, efficiency of performance and learning style. It is the contention of the framework that family fomentation may have significant relationship to the result-based performance quality of the senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. Moreover, determin-

ing which domains of family fomentation (emotional warmth, self-awareness, moral formation and parental management) would significantly influence the result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL is the intent of the study.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method of the study which includes research design, respondents of the study, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental quantitative research design to collect data and information. Using the quantitative research technique, the researcher can quantify the data to be collected and generalize findings from a sample to the target population. A quantitative research design, as defined by Fraenkel and Wallen (1993) as cited in Desimone and Garet (2019), is a strategy that allows one to study naturally occurring phenomena as well as answer questions about the distribution of and relationships between characteristics of people as they exist in their natural setting. Data were gathered from at least a portion of the population in order to assess the occurrence, distribution, and interrelationships of phenomena and variables as they occur in people’s lives. This kind of method was appropriate to use in the study because its purpose was to determine the relationship between family fomentation and result-based performance quality of TVL students.

Specifically, the descriptive-correlational design was used in this study to describe the extents as well as the relationship between or among variables. According to Doyle, Bryme, and Brady (2009), this design presented empirical data indicating the relationship between two or more factors. Creswell (2008) claimed that it used statistical models and forecasting approaches to understand and answer future questions. The study was correlational in nature because it measured and described the dependent and independent variables. Its goal was to identify and characterize phenomena as well as to explain variable relationships. In this study, descriptive method was employed to investigate the extents of family fomentation and result-based performance quality of TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. Furthermore, a correlational design was employed to assess the relationship between family fomentation and result-based performance quality of TVL students, as well as to determine the domain

of family fomentation (emotional warmth, self-awareness, moral formation, and parental management) that may influence the result-based performance quality of TVL students.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—In this study, the respondents were the selected one hundred fifty (150) secondary school TVL students from four (4) schools in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City who are taking up TVL-related strands. The respondents being part of the study were Grade 12 TVL students as they have been engaged in different hands-on activities particularly in their specialized subjects. They were also selected because soon they will be part of the workforce and the way how they mold by their parents and teachers will reflect to their work performance. Moreover, determining the demographic profile of the respondents such as sex, age, civil status and number of household members were not restricted. This study, on the other hand, used simple random sampling technique as the data being collected involve picking a certain number of respondents out of the total number of populations in the sampling frame (Antoniou, Geralexis Charitaki, 2020). In this study, selected public senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City were given the opportunity to give their rating on the extents of family fomentation and result-based performance quality.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The researcher gathered primary data from the senior high

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher underwent the following steps and procedures in gathering the data of this study:

- (1) Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher asked an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges with the consent of the thesis adviser to conduct the study. With the endorsement letter, the researcher sent a request letter to

school TVL students in four (4) secondary schools in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. The two variables of this study were assessed using two instruments: the family fomentation questionnaire was adapted from Ardila (2018), and the result-based performance quality questionnaire was adapted from Camara (2020). Each item was restructured to make the instruments more relevant to the current local educational context. The survey questionnaire was sent to three (3) experts for validation. The three (3) experts rated the instrument using a Validation Sheet. All of the experts' recommendations and opinions were followed. Following the validity test, the survey questionnaire was piloted with twenty (20) senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. Its reliability was then evaluated using Cronbach's alpha. Items with Cronbach alpha values greater than 0.70 were regarded as reliable, whereas items with values less than 0.70 were revised, according to Darren and Mallery (1999) as cited in Amirrudin, Nasution Supahar, 2021). Family Fomentation Questionnaire. Ardila (2018) came up with this. It's a self-report questionnaire with a Likert scale that focused on a detailed evaluation of the construct of family fomentation in terms of emotional warmth, self-awareness, moral formation and parental management. The rating scale for this variable is as follows:

- the DepeEd Division Office of Davao City through the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) to conduct the study. Then, the researcher asked permission to the respective school principal of the respondents in four (4) secondary schools to gather data within the month of April 2023.
- (2) Distribution and Retrieval of Survey Questionnaire. The researcher provided

Table 1. Interpretation of Range of Means for Family Fomentation of TVL Students

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.21 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The family fomentation of TVL students is always observed.
3.41 - 4.20	Extensive	The family fomentation of TVL students is oftentimes observed.
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Extensive	The family fomentation of TVL students is sometimes observed.
1.81 - 2.60	Less Extensive	The family fomentation of TVL students is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.80	Not Extensive	The family fomentation of TVL students is never observed.

Table 2. Interpretation of Range of Means for Result-Based Performance Quality of TVL Students

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.21 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The result-based performance quality of TVL students is always observed.
3.41 - 4.20	Extensive	The result-based performance quality of TVL students is oftentimes observed.
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Extensive	The result-based performance quality of TVL students is sometimes observed.
1.81 - 2.60	Less Extensive	The result-based performance quality of TVL students is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.80	Not Extensive	The result-based performance quality of TVL students is never observed.

the school principals and respondents with a timetable for administering the survey questionnaire. The distribution and retrieval of the questionnaires took place within the month of April 2023. The survey questionnaire was printed; hence, the researcher strictly adhered to IATF health protocols such as mask wearing and social distancing at all times. However, those respondents requested for online survey, a Google form

was considered.

- (3) Collation and Statistical Treatment of the Study. Following the successful administration and retrieval of the survey questionnaires, the data were compiled and tabulated. The data were then processed and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools, with the results interpreted. Following that, conclusions and recommendations were developed.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—In analyzing and interpreting the result of the study, the researcher used the following statistical tools: Mean was used to describe the extent of family fomentation of TVL students in terms of emotional warmth, self-awareness, moral formation, and parental management. Moreover, it was used to describe the extent of result-based performance quality of TVL students in terms of responsiveness, efficiency of performance and learning style.

Pearson's r was used to determine if significant relationship exists between family fomentation and result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression was employed to determine which domains of family fomentation (emotional warmth, self-awareness, moral formation, and parental management) influence the result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings and discussion based on the data gathered. The presentation is organized in four sections: first, the extent of family fomentation of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City; second, the extent of result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City; third, relationship between family fomentation and result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City; and fourth, Which domains of family fomentation significantly influence the result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City.

Presented in Table 3 is the summary of the extent of family fomentation of TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City in terms of emotional warmth, self-awareness, moral formation, and parental management. It reveals that the domain “moral formation” obtained the highest mean value among the four (4) domains ($\bar{x}=4.21$) which is described as “very ex-

tensive”, followed by the domain “emotional warmth” ($\bar{x}=4.14$) which is described as “extensive”. Then, the domain “parental management” obtained the following mean value ($\bar{x}=4.09$) which is described as “extensive”. However, the domain “self-awareness” obtained the lowest mean value among the four (4) domains ($\bar{x}=3.99$) which is described as “extensive”. It

Table 3. Summary on Family Fomentation of Senior High School TVL Students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City

No.	Domains of Family Fomentation	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Emotional Warmth	4.14	0.35	Extensive
2.	Self-Awareness	3.99	0.44	Extensive
3.	Moral Formation	4.21	0.48	Very Extensive
4.	Parental Management	4.09	0.48	Extensive
	OVERALL	4.10	0.44	Extensive

further reveals that the overall mean value on the extent of digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction is 4.10 which is described as “extensive”. This indicates that the respondents’ moral formation is always observed. On the other hand, the respondents’ emotional warmth, self-awareness, and parental management are oftentimes observed. This implies that the extent of family fomentation of TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City is oftentimes observed. Research identifies family’s environmental condition, values formation and parenting styles as the most important family-related factor influencing student achievement. Thus, while family fomentation is an important determinant of student achieve-

ment. As a parent, you must not only pay attention to the three factors listed above, but you must also pay attention to your responsibilities as a role model for your children (Cicchino, Amiel, 2018). However, Shek, Zhu, and Ma’s (2018) research suggests that parental impacts gradually fade away during the formative years of adolescence. Different parenting philosophies in respect to the four parenting attributes stated above contributed to early disparities in adolescent development. However, the disparity between teenagers that was first brought on by parental effects looked to be slowly closing. It’s probable that parental influence will decrease when a kid gains independence and starts to build major social networks outside of the household, such interactions with peers.

Table 4. Summary on Result-Based Performance Quality of Senior High School TVL Students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City

No.	Domains of Result-Based Performance Quality	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Responsiveness	4.13	0.42	Extensive
2.	Efficiency of Performance	4.30	0.43	Very Extensive
3.	Learning Style	3.96	0.70	Extensive
	OVERALL	4.13	0.52	Extensive

Shown in Table 4 is the summary on the extent of result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City in terms of responsiveness, efficiency of performance, and learning

style. It reveals that the domain “efficiency of performance” obtained the highest mean value among the three (3) domains (x=4.30) which is described as “very extensive”, followed by the domain “responsiveness” (x=4.13) which

is described as “extensive”, while the domain “learning style” obtained the lowest mean value among the three (3) domains ($x=3.96$) which is described as “extensive”. It reveals further that the overall mean value on the extent of result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City is 4.13 which is described as “extensive”.

This indicates that the efficiency of performance is always observed. Also, this indicates that the responsiveness and learning style are oftentimes observed. This implies that extent of result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City is oftentimes observed.

According to Malaya (2020), one of the most difficult problems in the educational setting after the pandemic is teaching technical, vocational, and livelihood students skills because it requires significant teacher adjustment in order for them to be effective and productive in closing the learning gap of the K–12 curriculum.

One of these difficulties is how to teach the various sorts of students in the TVL classroom the essential skills using a variety of methods. With the increased problems, instructors have discovered themselves in many viewpoints, particularly when putting into practice practical strategies that are focused on improving teacher effectiveness (Camara, 2020). However, according to Onofre Inocensi (2014), who was cited by Urrutia, Constantino, Sabordo, and Verzo (2019), senior high school core curriculum requirements are so demanding that pupils don’t have time to acquire the practical skills needed by the manufacturing sector. Furthermore, given that a student will be required to take 31 subjects, each of which requires 80 hours of actual classroom contact per semester, it will be impossible to fully prepare a TVL student to be ready for employment within two years. Very little time will be allowed for practical tasks, and much less time will be given to learning the skills needed for work.

Table 5. Relationship between Family Fomentation and Result-Based Performance Quality of TVL Students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City

Variables	Mean	SD	R	R ²	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision @ 0.05 level
Family Fomentation	4.10	0.44					
Result-Based Performance Quality	4.13	0.52	0.75	0.56	High	0.000	Reject Ho

Presented in Table 5 is the test of relationship between family fomentation and result-based performance quality of TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. It reveals that the relationship between family fomentation and result-based performance quality is high ($R=0.75$) and it is significant ($p\text{-value}=0.000<0.05$) at .05 level of significance. It

shows that the family fomentation significantly influenced the result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. This implies that when the family fomentation of senior high school TVL students is always observed, they would have high result-based performance quality. It further reveals that 56 percent ($R^2=0.56$)

of the variance result-based performance quality can be attributed for the family fomentation of senior high school TVL students, while the other 44 percent is caused by other factors. This implies that the family fomentation may be helpful in increasing the result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in cluster 1, Division of Davao City. This finding is congruent to a study conducted by Darling-Hammond (2019) Family fomentation and pupils' performance quality as measured by results are inextricably linked. The truth is that this crucial family-related aspect has a substantial impact on how well kids succeed in school. One of the aspects influencing the caliber of a student's performance is the information, abilities, disposition, and conduct of household members that assist the learning process. The most significant family-related element impacting student accomplishment, according to research, is the atmosphere of the family, values formation, and parenting methods. Parenting techniques are the most significant predictor of

student success, even though family fomentation is a crucial factor. The standard of parental supervision and guidance is inversely correlated with teacher credentials and student achievement. Similar factors include the support of family members, socioeconomic level, interactions between family members, and the state of the community (Cicchino Amiel, 2018). On the contrary, there is proof that a child's self-esteem is raised and their ability to interact with others is increased in a nurturing family setting. This self-assurance helps students grow in their capacity to adapt to various circumstances, which may be seen in the caliber of their work (Bruns Luque, 2019). According to Leinhardt (2018), a child's home environment may either impede or promote their overall development. Parents' attitudes are crucial; in environments where they are encouraging, children do better and grow more fully. Students gain from family interactions because they can develop their language, social, and intellectual abilities.

Table 6. Domains of Family Fomentation that Significantly Influence the Result-Based Performance Quality of TVL Students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City

Domains of Family Fomentation	B	BE	Beta	t-stat	p-value	Decision @ 0.05 level
Constant	4.13	0.03		115.23	<.001	Significant
Emotional Warmth	0.28	0.09	0.23	3.34	0.001	Significant
Self-Awareness	0.19	0.07	0.19	2.88	0.005	Significant
Moral Formation	0.03	0.07	-0.04	-0.51	0.612	Not Significant
Parental Management	0.51	0.06	0.55	8.17	<.001	Significant

Displayed in Table 6 is the test of influence of the domains of family fomentation towards the result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. It reveals that at 0.05 level of confidence, technology knowledge (B=0.21, p-value=0.009<0.05) and technological content

knowledge (B=0.41, p-value=0.000<0.05) significantly influenced the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction. It also shows that the relationship between digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL

dents is high ($R=0.77$) and 59 percent ($R^2=0.59$) of the variance in critical thinking disposition is attributed for digital learning functionality. It further shows that the model of critical thinking disposition is fit ($F=42.71$, $p\text{-value}=0.000;0.05$). The signs of statistically significant domains of family fomentation (emotional warmth, self-awareness, and parental management) are positive, indicating a direct positive relationship with result-based performance quality. This means that when family formation is always observed by the senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City, they would have high result-based performance quality. Consistently, according to Bond and Hayman (2021), the academic success of students has been found to be highly connected with the quality of family interactions at home. Additionally, it was shown that the physical surroundings of homes played a big role on pupils' academic progress. However, the child's qualities, however, have a major role in determining the family's effect (Allen, Cho Meier, 2020). In addition to psychological control, there appears to be a connection between parental warmth and many forms of children's social phobias. Moreover, when emotional warmth is always observed by the senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City, they would have high result-based performance quality. The findings of the study by Kowalski et al. (2019) contend that there are three main forms of parenting: emotional warmth, overprotection, and rejection. Positive parenting practices emphasize emotional warmth, whereas negative parenting practices emphasize rejection and overprotection. Children who get warm parental guidance may become more socially adept and form stable attachments. Lower parental warmth led to less self-regulation and externalizing behavior issues in preschoolers, according to Liu et al.'s 2019 research. Few hostile tendencies are seen among people raised in active parental environments. For instance, emotionally warm parenting creates a secure setting for bringing up children and educating them that helps them successfully control their negative emotions and lessen violent conduct. Furthermore, when self-awareness is always observed by the senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City, they would have high result-based performance quality. The result is associated with what La Valle and Arthur (2020) advocated for the provision of self-directedness and life skills through career counseling programs in schools in order to foster students' self-awareness. These skills include the ability to establish reasonable objectives, to consistently learn, and to bring value to their future workplaces. To excel in the job, one must possess these fundamental talents. Learning how to learn, proficiency in reading, writing, and computing, effective listening and oral communication skills, adaptability through creative thinking and problem-solving, personal management with strong self-esteem and initiative, interpersonal skills, the ability to work in teams or groups, fundamental technology skills, and leadership effectiveness are the skills that are most frequently mentioned (Parkman, 2019). On the contrary, self-awareness was a continuous and significant activity for secondary school pupils that affected the formation and development of human character. Humans have a propensity to assess themselves and express themselves differently at every stage of life (Layard, 2021). In addition, when parental management is always observed by the senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City, they would have high result-based performance quality. This is anchored to the study by Sharma (2020) which states that parenting management is significantly influenced by one's own parents. Children are encouraged to feel good about themselves and get along with others by this type of parenting style. A variety of interconnected factors, such as the child's age, gender, and temperament; the parents' personal-

ities, personal histories, financial situation, and similar factors; the needs of every family member; and the cultural values, determine how a particular parenting approach affects a specific child. However, according to Shek, Zhu, and Ma's (2018) research, parental impacts throughout adolescence's formative years tend to fade with time. Different parenting philosophies in respect to the four parenting attributes stated

above contributed to early disparities in adolescent development. However, the disparity between teenagers that was first brought on by parental effects looked to be slowly closing. It's probable that parental influence will decrease when a kid gains independence and starts to build major social networks outside of the household, such interactions with peers.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions that were drawn out of the findings of the study. This section further offers recommendations as to how the findings of this study can improve practice. This study aimed to ascertain the extents of family fomentation and result-based performance quality of senior high school Technical, Vocational and Livelihood students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City during the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to determine if relationship exists between the family fomentation and result-based performance quality of the students. Moreover, this study sought to determine which domains of family fomentation significantly influence the result-based performance quality of students. This study utilized the descriptive-correlational design to determine the extents of family fomentation and result-based performance quality and if they are significantly related. The respondents of this study were the selected one hundred fifty (150) secondary school TVL students from four (4) schools in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City, who were selected using simple random sampling technique. The researcher used adopted survey questionnaires to collect the necessary information. Data collection involved strict compliance of ethical considerations. Mean, Pearson's r , and multiple linear regression were used to analyze the data that had been collected.

4.1. Findings—The family fomentation of students is extensive. This means that the family fomentation of TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City is oftentimes observed. The result-based performance quality of students is extensive. This means that result-based performance quality of TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City is oftentimes observed. The result also shows that there is a significant positive relationship between the family fomentation and result-based performance quality of senior high TVL students. Moreover, the degree of the relationship is high. This means that when the family fomentation is always observed, the result-based performance quality of TVL students is high. Lastly, the result of the re-

gression analysis shows that emotional warmth, self-awareness and parental management are the domains of family fomentation that significantly influenced the result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn by the researcher:

The family fomentation of senior high school TVL students is oftentimes observed. This is evident as some of parents' roles and obligations towards their children are hindered due to lots of priorities at home. The result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students is oftentimes observed. Despite the different interventions made by schools and

stakeholders, still there are issues exist pertaining to the quality of performance among students. The result-based performance quality of senior high school TVL students would depend on their family fomentation. When their family fomentation is high, the result-based performance quality would escalate, which is very Moreover, it is evident that those senior high school TVL students who have high emotional warmth, self-awareness and parental management would always manifest a high result-based performance quality.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the foregoing conclusions, the following are recommended:

The Department of Education may set aside sufficient funds for the instructional and learning materials for senior high school TVL students. This allows for the acquisition of labo-

ratory materials genuine with high quality standard. The schools should intensify the public and private partnerships so that they can be assisted in the efficient delivery of TVL instruction through utilization of good facilities during the conduct of hands-on exercises and activities.

The School Governance Council should meet regularly and conduct “Balitaan” to gauge and discuss best practices both in school and at home which can serve as areas for improvement and reinforcement. The teachers may conduct reorientation program to parents during PTA meetings highlighting their important roles to their children especially in terms of values formation and appropriate parental management styles The same study can be conducted to confirm the identified themes using Exploratory Factor Analysis of Quantitative research design.

5. References

- Abun, F. D., & Cajindos, R. (2018). The effect of religion toward moral values of college students in Locos Sur, Philippines. *E-International Scientific Research Journal*, 4(3), 181-196.
- Agarao-Fernandez, E., & Guzman, A. B. (2020). Contextual Realities of Teacher Education in the Philippines. *Education and Research Policy Practice*, 4, 129–144.
- Agaton, C. B., & Cueto, L. J. (2020). Learning at home: Parents' lived experiences on distance learning during COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 901-911.
- Alipio, M. (2020). Predicting Academic Performance of College Freshmen in the Philippines using Psychological Variables and Expectancy-Value Beliefs to Outcomes-Based Education: A Path Analysis.
- Allen, T. D., Cho, E., & Meier, L. L. (2020). Work–family boundary dynamics. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 99-121.
- Amirrudin, M., Nasution, K., & Supahar, S. (2021). Effect of variability on Cronbach alpha reliability in research practice. *Jurnal Matematika, Statistika dan Komputasi*, 17(2), 223-230.
- Antoniou, A.-S., Geralexis, I., & Charitaki, G. (2020). Special Educators' Teaching Self-Efficacy Determination: A Quantitative Approach. *Psychology*, 8, 1642-1656.
- Ardila, A. (2018). Illiteracy: The neuropsychology of cognition without reading. *Archives of Clinical Neuropsychology*, 25(8), 689-712.
- Babaghayou, M., Labraoui, N., Ari, A. A. A., Lagraa, N., & Ferrag, M. A. (2020). Pseudonym change-based privacy-preserving schemes in vehicular ad-hoc networks: A survey. *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, 55, 102618.
- Ballantine, J. (2019). Raising competent kids: The authoritative parenting style. *Journal of Childhood Education*, 78(1), 46.
- Bayer, S., Johansen, G., & Ferm, C. (2018). Relations of Quality and Competence. *Finnish Journal of Music Education*, 65-81.
- Berk, E. L. (2021). *Development through the lifespan*. Allyn and Bacon, Boston.
- Bond, F., & Hayman, A. (2021). Every Moral Values of a child: A framework for an excellent education for all middle and high school students. Alliance for Excellent Education.
- Bradley, H. R., & Corwyn, F. R. (2020). Socioeconomic Status and Child Development. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53, 371-399.
- Bruns, B., & Luque, J. (2019). Great Teachers How to Raise Student Learning in Latin America and the Caribbean (Advance Edition). Washington, D.C. World Bank Group.

- Calpo, J. (2020, December 29). The quest for quality education continues. *Manila Bulletin*. Retrieved on October 21, 2021, from <https://mb.com.ph/2019/12/29/year-end-report-deped-in-2019-the-quest-for-quality-education-continues/>.
- Camara, J. S. (2020). Philippine Biology Education for a Curricular Innovation towards Industrial Revolution 4.0: A Mixed Method. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(1). Retrieved on February 12, 2023, from <https://asianjournal.org/online/index.php/ajms/article/view/212>.
- Caruana, et al. (2020). Practical education at home in a pandemic world. *Nature Chemistry*, 12, 780–783.
- Cicchino, N., & Amiel, M. (2018). Parenting strategies of parents with misbehaved children. *Springer Science & Business Media*, 64, 183-201.
- Cole, M., Cole, S. R., & Lightfoot, C. (2018). *The Development of Children, 5th Ed.* Worth Publishers, New York.
- Cox, T. D. (2018). Learning styles and admission criteria as predictors of academic performance of college freshmen. *Institute for Learning Styles Journal*, 1, 1-10.
- Creswell, J. W. (2008). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative approaches to research (3rd ed.)*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill/Pearson Education.
- Crompton, S., & Dennett, R. (2020). The latent structure of values formation problems in pupils living in poverty. *University of Zagreb, Faculty of Education and Rehabilitation Sciences*, 50, 1-12.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2019). *Quality Teaching: What is it and How can it be Measured?* Teachers College Press, 1234. Amsterdam Avenue, New York, NY 10027.
- Davis, B. (2021). What are the challenges in experiential learning? MVOrganizing. Retrieved on February 13, 2023 from <https://www.mvorganizing.org/what-are-the-challenges-in-experiential-learning/>.
- Davis, C. S., & Ellis, C. (2018). Family lives in rural: Auto-ethnographic narrative and the multi-ethnographic turn. In S. Hesse-Biber (Ed.). *The Handbook of Emergent Methods*. Guilford Press. New York.
- Desimone, L. M., & Garet, M. S. (2019). Classroom processes and positive youth development: Conceptualizing, measuring, and improving the capacity of interactions between teachers and students. *New Directions for Youth Development*, 121, 33–46.
- Dex, P., & Smith, C. (2019). What education schools aren't teaching about values education and what elementary teachers aren't learning? Washington, DC: NCTQ.
- Doyle, J., Bryme, S., & Brady, M. (2009). An overview of mixed methods research. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 14(2), 175-185.
- Erduran, S. (2020). Vocational Education in the Era of a Pandemic. *Sci & Educ*, 29, 233–235. Retrieved on March 11, 2023, from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11191-020-00122-w>.
- Essel, G., & Owusu, P. (2020). Causes of students' stress, its effects on their academic success, and stress management by students. *Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences*. Retrieved on March 4, 2023, from <https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/124792/Thesis%20Document.pdf?sequence=1>.

- Estrada, L. P. (2021, January). Are experiential strategies effective? *Rappler*. Retrieved on March 3, 2023, from <https://www.rappler.com/voices/imho/opinion-are-self-learning-modules-effective>.
- Fabrea, M., Robledo, D., & Lapada, A. (2020). Teachers' Covid-19 Awareness, Distance Learning Education Experiences and Perceptions towards Institutional Readiness and Challenges. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(6), 127-144.
- Felder, R. M., & Brent, R. (2020). Understanding student differences. *Journal of engineering education*, 94(1), 57-72.
- Gonzales, E. (2019, December 29). The quest for quality education continues. *Manila Bulletin*. Retrieved on March 1, 2023, from <https://mb.com.ph/2019/12/29/year-end-report-deped-in-2019-the-quest-for-quality-education-continues/>.
- Gumapac et al. (2021). Parents Involvement in Accomplishing Students Learning Tasks in the New Normal. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 4(7), 367-380.
- Ha, N. T. T. (2021). Effects of learning style on students achievement: experimental research. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S3), 329-339.
- Habibu, T., Al Mamun, M. A., & Clement, C. K. (2020). Difficulties faced by teachers in using ICT in teaching-learning at Technical and Higher Educational Institutions of Uganda. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, 1(7), 1-9.
- Hanushek, E. A., & Rivkin, S. G. (2021). Teacher Quality. *Handbook of the Economics of Education (Volume 2)*. Elsevier B. V.
- Huang, T. C. (2019). Do different learning styles make a difference when it comes to creativity? An empirical study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 100, 252-257.
- Johari Talib, Z. M., & Mamat, M. (2021). Effects of parenting style on children development. *World Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(2), 14-35.
- Joseph, M. V., & John, J. (2018). Impact of parenting styles on child development. *Global Academic Society Journal: Social Science Insight*, 1(5), 16-25.
- Khulusinniyah, K. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING MORAL VALUES IN EARLY CHILDREN. *Al-Risalah: Jurnal Studi Agama dan Pemikiran Islam*, 14(1), 230-245.
- Kowalski, R. M., Limber, S. P., & McCord, A. (2019). A developmental approach to cyberbullying: Prevalence and protective factors. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 45, 20-32.
- Kralik, R., & Mahrik, T. (2019). Interpersonal relationships as the basis of student moral formation. In *ICERI2019 Proceedings* (pp. 8896-8900). IATED.
- Kretzschmar, L., & Tuckey, E. C. (2020). The role of relationship in moral formation: An analysis of three tertiary theological education institutions in South Africa. In *die Skriflig*, 51(1), 1-8.
- Kumar, M. K. (2021). Challenges of Implementing Student-centered Strategies in Classrooms. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, 1224-1228.

- Labeste, V. (2020, November 28). The Role of Parents in Home Education. Retrieved on February 21, 2023, from <https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/sunstar-pampanga/20201128/281681142436238>.
- Lamanna, M. A., & Riedmann, A. (2018). *Marriages and families – Making choices and facing change*. Wadsworth Publishing Company, California.
- La Valle, K., & Arthur, N. (2020). Flexibility of working arrangements among parents, 23-54. Retrieved on March 9, 2023, from http://media.hoover.org/sites/default/files/documents/ednext20034_62.pdf.
- Layard, S. (2021). Diversity of families in a Workplace in Nyeri and Nairobi Districts. A Ph.D Thesis. Kenyatta University.
- Legate, N., Weinstein, N., & Przybylski, A. K. (2019). Parenting strategies and adolescents' cyberbullying behaviors: Evidence from a preregistered study of parent– child dyads. *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 48, 399-409.
- Leinhardt, G. (2018). Capturing Craft Knowledge in Teaching. Retrieved on February 26, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X019002018>.
- Liu, W., Liu, F., Chen, L., Jiang, Z., & Shang, J. (2019). Cognitive reappraisal in children: neuropsychological evidence of up-regulating positive emotion from an ERP study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 147.
- Malaya, B. (2020, August 5). DepEd Distance Learning: Here's what you need to know. Retrieved on February 23, 2023, from <https://www.whatalife.ph/deped-distance-learning-heres-what-you-need-to-know/>.
- Manti, S., & Licari, A. (2018). How to obtain informed consent for research. *Breathe*, 14(2), 145-152.
- McLeod, S. (2018). Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. *Simply Psychology*. Retrieved on February 21, 2023, from <https://www.simplypsychology.org/maslow.html>.
- Mercado, N. A. (2021, June). DepEd finds 155 errors in learning materials from Oct. 2020 to June 2021. *IQUIRET.Net*. Retrieved on February 3, 2023, from <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1445795/deped-finds-155-errors-in-learning-materials-from-oct-2020-to-june-2021>.
- Misko, J., & Priest, S. (2019). Students' Suggestions for Improving Their Vocational Education and Training Experience. *Occasional Paper*. National Centre for Vocational Education Research Ltd. PO Box 8288, Stational Arcade, Adelaide, SA 5000, Australia.
- Muthuprasad, T., Aiswarya, S., Aditya, K. S., & Jha, G. K. (2021). Students' perception and preference for online education in India during COVID-19 pandemic. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 3. Retrieved on March 3, 2023, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590291120300905?via%3Dihub>.
- Nardo, M. T. B. (2020, October). Modular Instruction Enhances Learner Autonomy. *Sciepub*. Retrieved on February 10, 2023, from <http://pubs.sciepub.com/education/5/10/3/index.html#:~:text=The%20use%20of%20modules%20is,in%20doing%20their%20individual%20tasks.&text=It%20directs%20students%20to%20practice%20or%20rehearse%20information>.

- Ngussa, N. K. (2021). Couples along the lines of the one-and-a-half earner model: A case of Nikuranga District, Tanzania. *Rural Development of Sokoine University of Agriculture: A Master's Degree Thesis*. Morogoro, Tanzania. Retrieved on March 2, 2023, from <http://www.suaire.suanet.ac.tz:8080/xmlui/bitstream/handle/123456789/1010/NEEMA%20KUSEKWA%20NGUSSA.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>.
- Nusseck, M., & Spahn, C. (2021). Musical Practice in Music Students During COVID-19 Lockdown. *Frontier Psychology*. Retrieved on February 23, 2023, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8165223/>.
- Osborne, J., Simon, S., & Collins, S. (2019). Attitudes towards distance learning: A review of the literature and its implications. *International Journal of Science Education*, 25(9), 1049-1079. Retrieved on February 15, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950069032000032199>.
- Parkman, L. (2019). An investigation of the impact of work-family arrangement. *ProQuest Dissertations Publishing*. Retrieved on March 1, 2023, from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/751915594?accountid=147155>.
- Pe Dangle, Y. R., & Sumaoang, J. D. (2020). The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in the Philippine Secondary Public Schools. *3rd International Conference on Advanced Research in Teaching and Education*. Retrieved on March 2, 2023, from <https://www.dpublication.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/27-427.pdf>.
- Quattrone, L., & Hopper, K. (2020). An examination of the relationship between flexible work arrangements, work-family conflict, organizational commitment, and job performance. *Management*, 23(2), 169-187.
- Quinones, M. T. (2020, July). DepEd clarifies blended, distance learning modalities for SY 2020- 2021. *Philippine Information Agency*. Retrieved on February 23, 2023, from <https://pia.gov.ph/news/articles/1046619>.
- Ravindran, B., & Baral, R. (2018). Factors Affecting the Work Attitudes of Indian Re-entry Women in the IT Sector. *Vikalpa*, 31-42.
- Republic Act 10173, s. 2012. Data Privacy Act. Retrieved on March 12, 2023, from <https://www.privacy.gov.ph/wp-content/files/attachments/ppt/DPO17Overview.pdf>.
- Sanders, W. L., & Rivers, J. C. (2019). Cumulative and Residual Effects of Teachers on Future Student Academic Achievement. *Knoxville, TN: University of Tennessee Value-Added Research and Assessment Center*.
- Saxon, D. P., Levine-Brown, P., & Boylan, H. R. (2021). Affective assessment for developmental students, part 1. *Research in Developmental Education*, 22(1), 1-4.
- Sharma, D. (2020). *Childhood, family, and Sociological Changes in India*. Oxford University Press, New Delhi, p. 21.
- Shek, D. T., Zhu, X., & Ma, C. M. (2018). The influence of parental control and parent-child relational qualities on adolescent internet addiction: A 3-year longitudinal study in Hong Kong. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 642.

- Singh, A. (2019). Teaching Filipino Values. *Illinois Reading Council Journal*, 42(2), 70-75. Retrieved on March 11, 2023, from <http://research.collegeboard.org/programs/sat/data/archived/cb-seniors2011/tables>.
- Tanik-Onal, N., & Onal, N. (2020). Teaching science through distance education during the Covid-19 pandemic. * *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 7*(4)*, 1898-1911.
- Tria, J. (2020). The COVID-19 Pandemic through the Lens of Education in the Philippines: The New Normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*, 1(1), 1-4.
- Urrutia, J. D., Constantino, I. J., Sabordo, N., & Verzo, J. (2019). Preferred Learning Styles of Technical-Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) Students in Public Senior High School in Sta. Rosa, Laguna. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, 8(2). Retrieved on March 11, 2023, from <https://www.ijrte.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/v8i2S11/B14200982S1119.pdf>.
- Yachina, N. (2021). The problem of spiritual and moral formation of personality. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 197, 1575-1579.
- Witro, D., Putri, B. A., Putri, L. A., & Oviensy, V. (2020). Role of The Family in Formation of Children Characters Based Moral Knowing, Moral Feeling, and Moral Action. *Tunas Cendekia: Jurnal Program Studi Pendidikan Islam Anak Usia Dini*, 3(1), 97-103.